

LEXICAL SEMANTIC CHARACTERISTICS OF ARABISMS IN UZBEKI AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES

Divanova Mokhira KHusanovna

Graduate Department of Urganch State University

Linguistics (*English*) 2nd year master's student

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Annotation: In this thesis, the use of Arabicisms in Uzbek and English languages, and the role of Arabicisms in written and oral speech from a linguistic point of view are discussed.

Key words: Linguistics, Arabism, English language, lexicon, semantics.

It is known that the scientific and technical revolution not only affects the productive forces of our society and the relations between them, their quantity and quality, but also has a transformative effect on all spheres of our life. Therefore, the main factor of this activity is, first of all, language. Because any changes in life and society take place initially in language and through it. The vocabulary of any national language, its total vocabulary is a phenomenon formed during the entire historical development of this nation. It is always moving and growing. The effectiveness of language development depends mainly on two factors, how to use its internal and external sources of growth. The expansion of international relations, the sincere generalization of the success and achievements of nations, especially the exchange of advanced experience in the fields of science, culture, industry, politics and the national economy, and the news and information from different parts of the world can be read by everyone in their native language. objective and necessary factors such as development have a beneficial effect on the development of languages, they enrich the content of the vocabulary at the expense of external sources.

The process of word acquisition in languages is always relevant. After all, not only the scientific community, but also our people should be aware of any process taking place in our national language. Enrichment of the language at the expense of acquisitions and the naming of new things and events through them, clarity of concepts and imaginations understood through them, is also relevant for every language owner and his conversation. If the natives of the language know how to use idioms and expressions, there will be fewer misunderstandings in their lives.

In the book "Lexicology of the Uzbek language", referring to the works of Russian linguists L. P. Krisin, N. M. Shansky, A. V. Kalinin, M. I. Fomina, V. V. Akulenko, N. Sharopov, the following opinion is expressed about the definition of word acquisition: "Acquisition - is the transfer of certain language elements from

one language to another." M. D. Stepanov and I. I. Chernyshev understand the introduction of foreign words into languages, the result of their assimilation, and their general set as word acquisition. It is known that every new word that comes from a foreign language naturally passes through the phonetic, orthographic and grammatical sieve of that language. In this case, the word undergoes some changes under the influence of certain laws of the language being learned in terms of reading, writing and structure, that is, foreign words are subject to a certain extent to the system of the receiving language. They can be read differently, written differently, omit or add some letters and sounds, and even completely change their shape and appearance.

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In the formation of words adapted to a certain language, we can often observe the compatibility of internal and external sources. That is, as a result of the influence of scientific and technical progress, trade, wars or the migration of immigrants, as well as the strengthening of cultural ties between peoples, words from one language to another have been assimilated. Such loanwords, in turn, over time have internal possibilities of the language, including phonetic changes in the word, by adding word-forming suffixes, creating simple pseudowords, creating compound words based on simple words, or otherwise creating lexical units with new meaning by expanding the meaning of the word. It prepares the ground for many words and phrases to appear in the language with tools.

We decided to continue the analytical data by looking at the historical development of another word adopted in the Arabic language. For example, the word "zamin" comes from the Arabic language and means "guarantor". This

word is explained in the explanatory dictionary as "the cause, the culprit of the unfortunate incident." In our opinion, it is slightly different from the Arabic guarantor. Because in the dictionary, the word "guarantor" is defined as a person who assures others about something or someone, assumes responsibility, guarantees, and is justified by examples in scientific works. . For example: I am sure that Ergash can be a good friend. We can see in the next example that this word is also used as a noun to express the meaning of a place. For example, "Northern, central and eastern part of Zomin district consists of lowland, and southwestern part consists of hills, hills and mountains". In such a case, in addition to its own meaning, it performs the function of synonymy with words expressing other lexical meanings.

In conclusion, the increase of the vocabulary in Uzbek linguistics has been carried out for centuries, by borrowing words from dialects, creating new words, moreover, as we have seen in this scientific analysis, borrowing words from other languages passes the development stage of linguistics, and in the future, along with other fields, aspects of linguistics will develop rapidly.

References:

1. Eshankulov B. The relation of Arabic lexical appropriations to paradigmatic asymmetry in the modern Uzbek literary language. Candidate of Philology... Dissertation. - Tashkent, 1996.
2. Mirzayev.M., Usmanov.S., Rasulov.I., Uzbek language. Tashkent: Teacher, 1966.
3. Kharatova, S. K. Goals And Tasks Of English Language Teaching. International Bulletin Of Engineering And Technology, 2(9).
5. Kharatova, S. K., & Ismailov, T. X. O. G. L. (2022). Use of innovative technologies in the educational process. Science and Education, 3(3), 713-718.
4. Mirtojiyev M. About some issues of homonymy// Issues of literary studies and linguistics. - Tashkent, 1963.
6. Mirtojiyev. M., Mahmudov.N., Language and culture. - Tashkent: Uzbekistan, 1992.

